

Kalila and Dimna – a game of stories

Technologies x Resources

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Connection to research

Imagine a video game that takes you on a journey through the wisdom and wonders of Kalila and Dimna, a collection of animal fables and a mirror of princes that journeyed across more than 40 languages, from Spain to Malaysia, over a period of almost 1500 years. This fascinating work of global literature has long been overshadowed by another collection of tales, the Thousand and One Nights, not only in humanities tradition and scholarship, but also in cultural memories and pop cultures. We, as a team of game enthusiasts and cultural studies experts, want to change that.

Our idea is to create an edutaining visual novel game that lets players experience history through storytelling while exploring the very topics in the heart of Kalila and Dimna research: authorship and intertextuality. Our game is inspired by the latest research on Kalila and Dimna, such as the European Research Council funded project "AnonymClassic" by 2017 Leibniz prize awardee Beatrice Gruendler (now extended as "Arabic Literature Cosmopolitan") which produced a critical edition and a digital archive of the different versions of the text and examined the role of anonymous copyists as co-authors. As multidisciplinary makers, we harness our creative curiosity to reinterpret Kalila and Dimna and its rich cultural heritage in a novel way, drawing from various references and viewpoints outside the academic sphere.

This gamified exploration thrives on the synergy of research at Freie Universität and research institutions in Berlin, as well as the indie game development scene in Berlin. It builds on Jonas Müller-Laackman's experience as a research software developer and researcher in multilingual digital humanities and digital scholarship services, and Victoria Mummelthai's work on disseminating and communicating the ERC project "AnonymClassic". Therewith, our project is embedded in a network of experts and institutions, mainly the cultural studies and humanities departments of Freie Universität, including their clusters of excellence "Epistemes in Motion" and "Temporal Communities". It is also associated with a project funded by the Berlin University Alliance (BUA) with the aim to bridge the digital divide between non-Latin scripts and digital humanities. Moreover, it draws upon the expertise and support of a community of scholars who promote multilingual digital humanities. Lastly, the institutional landscape of Berlin fosters our project's success, with the Staatsbibliothek holding 65 manuscripts related to Kalila and Dimna, and the Islamisches Museum hosting exhibitions such as "Cinderella, Sindbad & Sinuhe: Arab-German Storytelling Traditions," which further validates the cultural and historical significance of our project.

Idea and product innovation

By rethinking humanities research in the context of gaming, our idea is to create a visual novel game where players take on the role of a storyteller narrating tales of Kalila and Dimna to the caliph and his court in 8th century Baghdad. This timeframe is related to one of the earliest versions of Kalila and Dimna in Arabic supposedly having been translated from Middle Persian by 8th-century literate Ibn al-Muqaffa'. As storytellers, the players engage with two of the main topics of Kalila and Dimna research: authorship and intertextuality. In the same way as Kalila and Dimna is a prime example of the latter, the players employ acts of collecting stories, adapting, translating, redacting, overwriting, and reusing them; they find Kalila and Dimna's connections to earlier texts such as the fables of Aesop, as well as references in other contemporary and later texts such as The Thousand and One Nights. Like these, Kalila and Dimna did not spring from the pen of a single, identifiable author; thus, it is no static text with assured single authorship and corresponding authority for an original version but rather a fluid texture that changes with time, place, audience.

Within these dynamics of authorship and intertextuality, the game invites players to choose what kind of storyteller they want to be: What tales would one tell, and how would one tell them? With humor, suspense, emotion, persuasion? To whom would one tell them? To the caliph, his family, merchants, guests at court, children, copyists, and others? And how would one deal with their reactions? Their feedback, questions, requests, and emotions? These are some of the questions that the game poses to the players. Their choices not only shape their own story with branching paths – with some including mini-games or puzzles related to the plot – and multiple endings, but also their reputation, relationships and outcomes with different characters and factions in the court and beyond. As players engage with different characters and places, they learn about the political and social circumstances of the Abbasid era and its history. The game will have a 2D art style inspired by illustrations of Kalila and Dimna manuscripts; it will feature an immersive soundtrack and multilingual voice acting. Our aim is to let the players not only tell the stories themselves but to become cultural explorers of the rich environment of their creation and transmission.

We propose a novel fusion of three distinct domains: literary scholarship, multilingual digital humanities, and game design. Each domain has its own logic, tools, and goals, but they can also enrich each other and open new horizons for exploration and expression. By weaving these three domains together, our idea seeks to create a unique product that uses game design as a medium to convey literary scholarship and multilingual digital humanities.

Some aspects that make this idea innovative are:

- It draws on Kalila and Dimna, a collection of fables that originated in India in the third century CE and was translated into many languages, including Arabic, Persian, Hebrew, Spanish, and Georgian. It is a central text of premodern world literature with a spread easily comparable to the Bible.
- It uses game design as a medium to communicate literary scholarship and multilingual digital humanities, often seen as separate or even incompatible fields. It challenges the conventional boundaries between academic research and artistic creation, between textual analysis and visual representation, between historical context and contemporary relevance.
- It engages players in an interactive and immersive experience that allows them to access and appreciate Kalila and Dimna as a literary work with intertextual connections with other texts from different traditions or languages. In a future version, a free mode may be added, which allows players to express their own creativity by creating their own stories with elements from Kalila and Dimna or other texts.

Customer value and market

We identify at least four potential target audiences: educators, researchers, cultural institutions, and gamers – all of for whom four aspects are of value: first, to gain historical awareness for the so-called Golden Age of Islam from the 8th to 13th century as a period of scientific, economic, and cultural flourishing especially in and around Baghdad; second, to learn about the fluidity of stories in their oral and written literary and cultural traditions; third, to explore their own creativity as raconteurs and, by that, living a cultural practice that is crucial to Arab and other Middle Eastern traditions: the art of oral storytelling; fourth, simply to play a game.

Educators will gain from the game's educational value that lets players explore the diverse cultural setting of 8th century Baghdad and beyond, multiple languages such as Arabic and Persian, and world views through the versions of Kalila and Dimna. How about introducing students to manuscript and script cultures, in the spirit of the historical narrative-driven game *Pentiment* with its heavily stylized manuscript art, ink-based strategy game *Inkulinati* inspired by medieval marginalia, or puzzle game *Type:Rider* uncovering the secrets of fonts and characters?

For researchers working on topics such as comparative literature, translation studies, culture studies, or digital humanities and who want to share their findings or engage with their sources in different ways, the game presents a novel approach to presenting humanities research such as

authorship and intertextuality in other garb, that is in the form an experiential story set in its relevant historical context. How would it be to discover the literary and historical significance of the Epic of Gilgamesh, the oldest surviving work of literature that tells the story of the legendary king of Uruk and his quest for immortality, using the captivating and interactive medium of video games?

Cultural institutions who want to foster intercultural dialogue or display their collections will appreciate the game's potential to increase awareness and admiration of Kalila and Dimna as a rich and diverse cultural heritage belonging to global humanity. How would it be to feature DLCs that include further aspects of Kalila and Dimna, such as illustrations, commentaries, adaptations, etc. from different museums or libraries around the world, e.g., by partnering with cultural institutions such as British Library, Bibliothèque nationale de France, or Qatar National Library?

In terms of gamers or gaming-interested parties, the idea appeals to the rising market of edutainment games, which combine entertainment with education to offer digital learning solutions. A report by Grand View Research valued this market at USD 3.9 billion in 2019 and expected it to grow at a CAGR of 17% from 2020 to 2027. Moreover, within the established gaming market, it taps into a niche but lucrative market of educational games and visual novels. Surveys by SteamSpy suggest a potential market for visual novel games in both Western and Eastern countries. Ideally, the game marks the beginning of insights from humanities and cultural studies research being made approachable and valuable beyond the communities of academia, in our case through a contemporary medium like video games.

Practicability

Creating a visual novel game inspired by the Kalila and Dimna manuscripts and tradition is a challenging project involving at least five aspects in terms of feasibility. One of the main aspects is the quality of the storytelling, which should be engaging, interactive, and diverse, reflecting the intertextual nature of the source material. Another aspect is the integration of the story and the game environment, which should be smooth and immersive, allowing the players to explore and influence the historical and cultural context of the Abbasid era. A third aspect is the 2D art style, which should be faithful to the illustrations of the manuscripts, but also appealing and accessible to modern gamers, using colors, animations, and effects that enhance the visual experience. A fourth aspect is the marketability and appeal of the game, which should be designed in a way that attracts and educates potential players who may not be familiar with visual novels or Middle Eastern culture, using features such as multilingual voice acting, branching paths, mini-games, and puzzles. To conclude, reaching some of the intended audiences poses more challenges than engaging gamers on platforms such as Steam or Epic. Therefore, we will devise strategies to make the game available beyond the confines of gamer-centric storefronts and reconnect it with its roots in the humanities, cultural and area studies – by that also stepping into gamifying these disciplines.

To commercialize our idea, we have three potential avenues to explore:

- Partnering with a reputable indie game studio that shares our passion for combining academic rigor with artistic expression. This would boost our resources, feedback, and network, but also require compromise and reliance on the studio's performance.
- Starting our own indie game studio specializing in humanities-research-based games. This would grant us full creative freedom and potential recognition, but also pose challenges such as resources, network, legal protection, or competition from established game studios.
- Crowdfunding our project through platforms like Kickstarter or Patreon. This would allow us to raise funds from our supporters, engage with our audience, test our idea, receive feedback, and keep creative control, but also expose us to risks such as failing to meet our goal and disappointing our backers.

Our vision is to create a visual novel game that brings to life the Kalila and Dimna manuscripts, translations, adaptations, and their intertextualities as a rich source of humanities research and presents it in an engaging and accessible way for non-academic audiences, beyond the conventional forms of scholarly publications.